

Culture and Governance: Promoting sustainable social change, case study: Cámara Popular del jirón Amazonas in the city of Lima-2024

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ABSTRACT: The objective of this study was to determine how cultural innovation and governance are related in promoting sustainable social change in the Popular Chamber of Jirón Amazonas, Lima–2024. The problem posed was: How are cultural innovation and governance related in this context? The general hypothesis established that cultural innovation is positively related to governance. The research was conducted using a basic quantitative paradigm with a bivariate correlational design. The population consisted of 201 entrepreneurs, from which a sample of 130 was obtained. The results showed that cultural innovation is positively related to governance, presenting a high and significant correlation. It is concluded that cultural innovation is a key factor in strengthening governance and promoting sustainable social change in urban communities.

KEYWORDS: Cultural Participation, Preservation of Cultural Heritage, Development of New Forms of Expression, Inclusion and Cultural Diversity, Innovation in Cultural Education.

INTRODUCTION

In a global context where cities face a series of economic, social, and environmental challenges, cultural innovation and effective governance have emerged as crucial tools for promoting sustainable social change. The Popular Chamber of Jirón Amazonas, in Lima, is a representative example of this problem: it is a historic space for commerce and social gathering that, despite its cultural relevance, shows limitations related to economic informality, low citizen participation, and insufficient coordination between public and private actors. This situation directly affects the sustainable development of the community and restricts its ability to adapt to social and economic changes. In this context, the research seeks to address how cultural innovation and effective governance can contribute to the resolution of these problems, promoting sustainable social change in the community. Therefore, by integrating local culture into the development of policies and projects, a sense of belonging and social cohesion can be fostered, while promoting inclusive economic development. Cultural innovation involves not only the preservation of cultural identity, but also its adaptation and evolution in response to contemporary challenges. The Popular Chamber of Jirón Amazonas, as a representative body of merchants and other local actors, plays a central role in articulating the needs and aspirations of the community. However, the lack of a solid and participatory governance framework has limited its ability to influence public policy and implement strategies that promote cultural innovation and sustainable development.

The purpose of this study is to generate scientific evidence that allows us to understand how cultural innovation influences governance and contributes to promoting sustainable social change in the Popular Chamber of Jirón Amazonas. In this way, it seeks to provide useful knowledge for the formulation of public policies, the strengthening of citizen participation, and the preservation of cultural heritage in urban communities.

The background that has guided the development is shown below

Table 1.

INTERNATIONAL BACKGROUND

Author (s)	Title	Development
De Araújo Uribe (2020)	Organizational culture and innovation: a review of the literature.	A systematic descriptive study was conducted based on publications between 1988 and 2019 in the Scopus database. A total of 70 articles were examined. The results indicate that among the organizational aspects that influence the

		creation of an innovative culture in companies are leadership, organizational structure, and learning and knowledge processes. In addition, cultural aspects related to beliefs, values, norms, communication, creativity, participation, empowerment, motivation, and entrepreneurial attitude have a decisive impact on organizational activities.
Citrato (2020)	Culture of innovation, ideas for its development.	Innovation and intellectual property are complex and uncertain fields due to the diversity of professionals and sectors involved, each with their own approaches and languages, in a context where intangible assets exceed tangible assets in value and are becoming increasingly important economically. This transition highlights the importance of knowledge as an unlimited resource, unlike material goods, which are finite.
Pérez (2019)	Description of the decision making process of the Innovation and Competitiveness Fund (FIC).	Chile is currently experiencing a crisis of legitimacy stemming from trust in the dictatorship's promise of modernization, which prioritized public policy management to the detriment of the public ethos, affecting the relationship between institutions and civil society. Therefore, our interest lies in analyzing the decision-making process of the Competitiveness and Innovation Fund (FIC) in the Tarapacá region. In methodological terms, an interpretive approach has been used to identify and delimit the phenomenon in question. Semi-structured interviews were used to collect information, which has been analyzed using grounded theory. Among the main findings, we highlight the identification of the key actors that influence the decision-making process in the governance of the Tarapacá region, as well as the determination of the most relevant administrative, political, and cultural factors in that process.

Note: Prepared by the author. Table

Table 2

NATIONAL BACKGROUND

Author (s)	Title	Development
Orbegoso Venturo (2023)	Public management and governance for the development of communities	Public management and governance are crucial issues in Latin American countries, requiring reflection on the part of the academic community, as their effectiveness and efficiency have a direct impact on the quality of life of the population. Therefore, the main objective of this book is to examine, from an academic perspective, various aspects related to public administration in Peru and South America. The first chapter begins with a reflection on governance and the common challenges affecting the region, such as corruption, citizen insecurity, inadequate management of environmental problems such as waste management, and violence against women.

<p>Salas et al. (2023)</p>	<p>Cultural resonance in companies for the support of entrepreneurial initiatives</p>	<p>This work seeks to analyze perspectives on supporting entrepreneurial projects and understand how entrepreneurship drives the creation of brands and businesses that benefit local communities. Therefore, the main objective is to contrast the positions of different authors on the most appropriate strategies for supporting entrepreneurial initiatives. Specifically, it seeks to define the concepts of cultural resonance and entrepreneurship, analyze the key strategies for promoting it, and highlight entrepreneurship as an essential element, considering cultural resonance as a way to align the values of entrepreneurs with those of their target audience. However, the study reveals that cultural resonance favors business success, but it is not the only strategy, and there is still little research on the subject.</p>
<p>Morales & Roman Saavedra (2021)</p>	<p>Managerial entrepreneurial culture in the development of innovation in Piura PYMEs – 2019.</p>	<p>The study analyzed the influence of entrepreneurial management culture on innovation in SMEs in Piura in 2019, with a sample of 382 companies. Using a nonexperimental correlational descriptive design, the results showed that this culture has a significant influence on innovation: 9.9% of companies with a high entrepreneurial culture developed innovation, while 59.7% with a low culture did not. The hypothesis was confirmed by the Chi-square test ($X^2_{Cal}=576.068 > X^2_{Tab}=9.4877$).</p>

Note: Prepared by the author

CULTURAL INNOVATION

According to the commonly accepted notion, it is defined as a collection of values and beliefs acquired over time, which become basic assumptions about expected behavior in the company. Schein (1985), an MIT scholar recognized for his contributions to this topic, described it as a set of basic assumptions learned and shared by a specific group, which are considered valid for addressing internal problems and adapting to the group's external context. If management believes that changing cultural innovation involves directly influencing the values and beliefs of employees, the task may seem difficult. However, through their daily practice and example in the way they exercise their responsibility and develop relationships, senior managers are constantly demonstrating what they value and expect from their employees. The values and beliefs that make up the company's cultural innovation are largely the result of experiences accumulated over time, suggesting that changing the way employees are managed and developed can promote cultural innovation that is conducive to innovation.

GOVERNANCE

Governance is understood as the set of processes, mechanisms, and structures through which public, private, and social actors make decisions, coordinate actions, and manage resources to achieve collective goals. According to Rhodes (1996), governance is a model of leadership characterized by interdependent networks of actors who cooperate beyond the state. For his part, Gobernanza (1992) defines it as "the way in which power is exercised in the administration of a country's economic and social resources for development." Likewise, Mayntz (2001) points out that governance implies new forms of coordination between the state, the market, and civil society.

In this regard, the study posed the following general problem: To determine how cultural innovation and governance are related: Promoting Sustainable Social Change, Case Study: Promoting Sustainable Social Change, Case Study: Cámara Popular del Jirón Amazonas in the city of Lima -2024

METHODOLOGY

The study was developed under a basic quantitative paradigm, with a non-experimental, cross-sectional, and bivariate correlational design, aimed at determining the relationship between cultural innovation and governance in the Popular Chamber of Jirón

Amazonas in Lima during the year 2024. The research was conducted at the Popular Chamber of Jirón Amazonas, located in the Historic Center of Lima. The population consisted of 201 entrepreneurs registered with the Popular Chamber of Jirón Amazonas. The sample was determined by simple random probability sampling, obtaining a total of 130 entrepreneurs. The sample size was calculated using the formula for finite populations, with a confidence level of 95% and a margin of error of 5%. A structured questionnaire was used, designed based on the dimensions of the variables cultural innovation and governance. The instrument was validated by experts and its reliability was tested using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, which reached a value of 0.82, indicating high internal consistency. The data collected were processed using SPSS statistical software version 28. Descriptive statistics were applied to characterize the population, and Spearman's Rho correlation test was used to establish the relationship between the variables, as the data were non-parametric.

The research was conducted in accordance with ethical principles, and informed consent was obtained from the participants, who were informed about the purpose of the study, the confidentiality of the data, and the exclusive use of the information for academic purposes.

RESULTS

Table 1. Reliability statistics of the instrument.

VARIABLE EVALUATED	CRONBACH'S ALPHA	INTERPRETATION
Cultural Innovation	0.825	Very high reliability
Governance	0.826	Very high reliability

Table 2. Frequencies by Variable and Dimension

Variable / Dimension	Low (%)	Acceptable (%)	Good (%)
Variable 1: Culture of Innovation	16,9	65,4	17,7
D1: Cultural Participation	6,9	67,7	25,4
D2: Preservation of Cultural Heritage	9,2	60,8	30,0
D3: Inclusion and Cultural Diversity	6,2	60,0	33,8
D4: Development of New Forms of Expression	9,2	62,3	28,5
D5: Innovation in Cultural Education	18,5	49,2	32,3
Variable 2: Competitive Strategy	18,5	62,3	19,2
D1: Citizen Participation	22,3	66,9	10,8
D2: Public-Private Partnership	16,2	63,1	20,8
D3: Innovative Cultural Policies	26,2	65,4	8,5
D4: Transparency and Accountability	10,8	65,4	23,8
4			
D5: Decentralization and Local Empowerment	13,8	65,4	20,8

Note: Prepared by the author.

The analysis shows that both the Culture of Innovation and Competitive Strategy are perceived as mostly positive, with the acceptable level predominating in most dimensions. The areas with the highest ratings include Cultural Participation, Preservation of Cultural Heritage, and Cultural Inclusion and Diversity, with percentages above 60% at the acceptable level and more than 25% at the good level. In Competitive Strategy, most dimensions are at acceptable levels, although Innovative Cultural Policies has the highest proportion at a low level (26.2%), highlighting the need for improvement.

Correlation between Cultural Innovation and Governance (Spearman's Rho)

Table 2. Correlation between Cultural Innovation and Governance
Correlaciones

	Variable 1 Cultura de Innovación (Agrupada)	Participación Cultural D1V1 (Agrupada)	Preservación del Patrimonio Cultural D2V1 (Agrupada)	Inclusión y Diversidad Cultural D3V1 (Agrupada)	Desarrollo de Nuevas Formas de Expresión D4V1 (Agrupada)	Innovación en la Educación Cultural D5V1 (Agrupada)	Variable 2: Estrategia Competitiva (Agrupada)		
Rho de Spearman	Variable 1 Cultura de Innovación (Agrupada)	Coefficiente de correlación	1.000	,772**	,762**	,698**	,774**	,683**	,745**
		Sig. (bilateral)		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
		N	130	130	130	130	130	130	130
	Participación Cultural D1V1 (Agrupada)	Coefficiente de correlación	,772**	1.000	,726**	,750**	,803**	,581**	,690**
		Sig. (bilateral)	0.000		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
		N	130	130	130	130	130	130	130
	Preservación del Patrimonio Cultural D2V1 (Agrupada)	Coefficiente de correlación	,762**	,726**	1.000	,791**	,764**	,546**	,735**
		Sig. (bilateral)	0.000	0.000		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
		N	130	130	130	130	130	130	130
	Inclusión y Diversidad Cultural D3V1 (Agrupada)	Coefficiente de correlación	,698**	,750**	,791**	1.000	,711**	,508**	,693**

Note: Prepared by the author

The Spearman test analysis revealed that there is a high and statistically significant positive correlation between the Cultural Innovation variable and the Governance variable (Rho = 0.745; p = 0.000). This means that as Cultural Innovation increases in the organization, Governance practices are also strengthened, confirming the relationship proposed in the hypothesis.

Likewise, significant positive correlations were found between the dimensions of Cultural Innovation and Governance. The following values stand out: Preservation of Cultural Heritage (Rho = 0.735), Cultural Inclusion and Diversity (Rho = 0.693), Cultural Participation (Rho = 0.690), Innovation in Cultural Education (Rho = 0.679), and Development of New Forms of Expression (Rho = 0.672).

These results indicate that all dimensions of Cultural Innovation contribute significantly to strengthening Governance, with Preservation of Cultural Heritage being the dimension with the highest correlation.

DISCUSSION

The relationship between cultural innovation and governance has been the subject of growing interest in recent years, especially in the context of promoting sustainable social change. The assertion that "cultural innovation is positively related to governance, promoting sustainable social change" is based on the idea that culture is not only a reflection of society, but also an engine of social transformation. This relationship will be discussed in detail below, addressing how cultural innovation can influence governance and, in turn, how effective governance can enhance cultural innovation to generate sustainable social change.

The results show a positive and significant correlation between Cultural Innovation and Governance, with a Spearman's Rho coefficient of 0.745 and a significance level of p = 0.000, confirming that the former directly influences the strengthening of the latter within the context of the entrepreneurs of the Amazonas People's Chamber in Lima (2024). In addition, it was evident that all the dimensions evaluated—Citizen Participation, Public-Private Collaboration, Innovative Cultural Policies, Transparency Accountability, and Decentralization-Local Empowerment—showed strong associations, with correlation values above 0.67, indicating a general trend toward the integration of innovative cultural practices as a driver of sustainable social change.

Compared to international cases, the results are consistent with those of Landry (2012), who shows how creative cities such as Barcelona and Berlin have revitalized their territories through innovative cultural policies, promoting sustainable development. Similarly, Capillé (2018) highlights that Medellín achieved profound social change through the integration of cultural innovation and participatory governance, a result similar to that observed in this research.

It was found that each of the dimensions of governance has a relevant relationship with cultural innovation. Citizen participation, for example, has a coefficient of $\rho = 0.690$; $p = 0.000$. This figure is consistent with Rhodes' (1996) assertion that contemporary governance is a process based on collaborative networks in which citizens are essential actors. Cooperation between the private and public sectors ($\rho = 0.735$) also shows that cultural innovation generates opportunities to create strategic alliances that foster collective solutions. This finding was corroborated by Landry (2000) in his study of creative cities such as Berlin and Barcelona, where cross-sector collaboration has been fundamental to sustainable progress.

CONCLUSION

The study showed that cultural innovation has a significant relationship with various key factors of sustainable social change in the case of entrepreneurs from the Popular Chamber of Jirón Amazonas in the city of Lima – 2024. A strong relationship was identified with governance, citizen participation, collaboration between the public and private sectors, innovative cultural policies, as well as transparency and accountability, demonstrating that these components are essential for strengthening sustainable social processes. Likewise, a moderate relationship was found with decentralization and local empowerment, suggesting that, although cultural innovation drives transformation, it requires greater territorial and community strengthening to enhance its effects. Overall, the findings highlight the need to integrate cultural innovation into local development strategies and public policies as an engine of sustainable social change.

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Cite this Article: Tantavilca, R. (2025). Culture and Governance: Promoting sustainable social change, case study: Cámara Popular del jirón Amazonas in the city of Lima-2024. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 8(10), pp. 5007-5012. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V8-i10-14>